

The importance of using the heritage of our Great Scientists in lifelong education and preparing students for family life

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Abstract: The article talks about the importance of using the creative heritage of our scientists in organizing the educational process of students and preparing them for life, developing in them the positive qualities of the concept of family.

Keywords. Abdullah Avloniy, Sadriddin Ainiy, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Social network, Youth education.

At a time when times are changing and developing more and more, much attention in our country is paid to the field of science and education. It would be an exaggeration to say that our president's attention to the issue of education, which is. Today, the problem is relevant not only for the president of our country, but also for all members of our society. For this reason, the implementation of a number of activities in the education and training system is uniform. one of the most pressing problems of our country today.

This can already be seen from the changes taking place in the public education system. One of them is the attention paid today to the spheres of education, science and sports in our republic. The importance of this can be judged by the acceptance of the concept. "Continuing education".n fact, time passes and science is updated, as can be seen from the example of new discoveries, directions and various possible innovations.

But the speed of information today cannot be considered as low as the speed of its receipt. As throughout the world, various correct and incorrect information comes to our country through the media and social networks. Unfortunately, not everyone can understand this. either a lie or the truth. Especially among schoolchildren, such different topics are discussed a lot. There are young people among us who don't even want to think about family stability, the responsibilities of femininity and motherhood, masculinity and fatherhood, respect for elders, and honoring parents. Carrying out the education system in harmony with upbringing is one of the most important factors in organizing educational work and preparing young people for family live. Connect the educational process with the education system, prepare young people for family life, use the works of Abdullah Avloni, Farobi, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Sadriddin Aini in classes, introduce them into life, instill in consciousness For young people, family and life are complex, but great. This serves as a tool for them

to understand. On education and morality: “Turkish Gulistan or Morality” by Avlaniy, “Kutadgu Bilig” by Yusuf Khos Hajib, “Education of Youth” by Sadriddin Ayniy, Farabiy. “City of Virtuous People” In their works they gave a number of information about moral, scientific, aesthetic knowledge, experience and the results of their acquisition and application in the life of the education system. The relationship of girls to their family, spouse and other family members, raising children, duties and responsibilities of boys to their husbands are explained in detail. Ample information is also given about good deeds, frugality, family management and the environment. Using the heritage of our great scientists in the implementation of educational activities in educational institutions together with the field of education serves to achieve high results in the humane and educational processes. In conclusion, I can say that every nation has the values of its historical and cultural heritage and traditions that have been formed since ancient times, and all of them remind the representatives of this people of who they are.

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